

USE OF ADVERBS AND INTRODUCTORY SECTIONS IN HADITH TEXTS

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Annotation . This in the article islam of religion holy source was hadith of the texts to himself typical features , motivations and their content in expression held place about way used about information is given.

Key words : hadith , text , motivation , content , address , speech effectiveness .

Imperative is the speaker's speech directed person , thing or nature event , existence stated words do not urge is called Hadith texts of urges participation of content at the opening main from tools is one In Hadith texts incentives mainly , Allah , our Prophet ass companions and family members or whole public (II-III person) . will come . of the hadith text the main essence islam religion , God introduction , duty and responsibilities , living style reform to do explain , illuminate to give , in themselves there is has been to problems to find a solution , this the goal because of the hadith in the texts incentives a lot occurs .

Hadith texts main in parts Companions of the Prophet , family members or public by appeal done , their own problematic situations , questions answer will receive :

Ibn Abbas God willing anhu : " Mr Messenger of Allah to their presence Abd - ul - Qays from the tribe one the team came _ Peace be upon him alayhi and sallam : " Which one is this?" team ?" they asked . Guests "We Rabia " We are from the people , " they said . " Okay Welcome , please , don't be embarrassed come !" - they said Rasulullah as " **Yo Messenger of God** , we are yours to you only in the month of Rajab come we will be (rajab in the month tribes aro war is forbidden)...";

"... This see Mr Rasulullah's blessed two from his eyes whirling young flowed. Then Sa'd : " **Yo Messenger of God** , what did you do ?...";

Aisha God willing anho narrative they do : " People Mr To Rasulullah : " **Yo Messenger of God** , around here recently from the polytheists get rid of being to Islam entered the peoples are not, they are to us meat cause they stand They are own animals while slaughtering Allah of the Almighty the name whether they say or not, that 's it we are unaware " - they said . Then His Highness : " You yourselves Allah of the Almighty the name they said .

Above in the texts addressees " Yo " Rasulullah " . is doing and own thoughts , questions , problems from the addressee answer they are getting That is question and a tree in sentences incentives is being used . "In this way appeal to do respect of expression to himself typical appearance is ". The following in samples and our Prophet as _ in his speech urges seeing let's go :

Maoz ibn Jabal narrative They say : " **Oh , Maoz** , you know Allah of the Almighty own in his servants right they said .

Companion Famous narrative they do : " Rabza." said Abu Zarr in the place he is both a slave and a shepherd wearing coming without i saw Why one different get dressed I asked .

Abu Zarr : "Me one the person (Bilol), **oh , black wife's child!** - an insult I did .
Messenger of Allah to me : " O Abu Zarr , his mother an insult you do , you out of ignorance
there is "- they said and again " Your brothers are your servants . Allah may Allah bless him
and grant him peace them yours into your hands handed over put. Who's brother in hand if
from eating let him eat "; Ibn Abbas God willing Anhudan : " Hey Abbas ! Hey my uncle ! Give it
to you can i eat A gift to you Can I do it ?".

Above in the examples " **Yo Maoz** ", " **O Abu Zarr** ", " **O Abbas** ", " **Hey I am** my uncle
is being done . In Hadith texts this such as hey such as to call exclamations do not urge with
together apply through speech effectiveness reinforced . " Hey "my uncle " in the infinitive -
ginam download and -m person -number suffix _ through caress meaning is being observed .
"... hey black wife's child " urge while expanded , compound without is coming In Hadith texts
incentives not only exclamation with together , also the word compound in the style of ie
expanded can also be found in since :

" **O community of Muhammad !** To God I swear , if I knew when you know was really
little laughing a lot cried will be they said . (Five great Muhaddis by narrative done);

Shaqiq God willing anhudan narrative It will be said : " **O Amir al - mo'minin** , you
from this if you are not afraid it will be because you together that's it conspiracy in the middle
one closed the door hole being standing ";

Narrated by Imam Muslim did in the hadith : "... **Hey mo of believers mother** ,
Rasulullah peace be upon him alayhi my vassal at night position to be about speaking I said . "
Yes ayuhal muzammil " suarsini have you read ?" they said . I (Said inb Hisham): " I have
studied ," I said . " Of course , God may Allah bless him and grant him peace this of the surah in
the beginning at night position to be obligatory did. Messenger of Allah peace be upon him
alayhi vassal and companions one year at night at night position they were Even legs swollen
went Allah may Allah bless him and grant him peace push it the end Ten hold for two months
stood up Then this push it At the end of relief fell , "- they said ." So , the hadith in the texts " O
Muhammad's Ummah " , " O Amir al- mo'minin " , " O believers like his mother compound title
or nickname as there are also incentives .

Above from samples come out , that's it conclusion what we do maybe a hadith of texts
content , essence illuminated in giving impulses , the main from tasks one performs. After all,
the hadiths until us arrived the arrival is here that's it question - in the answers do not urge
the owners through narrative done arrived may have come

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